

NDAC/LO/097
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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, Vb.
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This short note contains some supplementary details about the reductions for the equal-magnitude 'half-slit-period' systems treated in NDAC/LO/095 (Paper V).

1. Output from the Preprocessing

As explained in Paper V, it is very advantageous to have some 'new' second harmonic information from the Preprocessing. One idea would be to have the second harmonic data only replacing the first harmonic in the critical FOV-passages. In Paper V, I had made some few test solutions for this case, which seemed to show results close to the 'optimum' N2-solution. After more thorough tests, this no longer holds. The 'alternating' output is better than the old, but markedly poorer than a 'full' new scheme with both first harmonic and second harmonic data given for all observations. As preliminarily agreed at the June RGO-meeting, the output from the Preprocessing to the Double Star processing should be changed according to this.

2. The grid-search

A remaining problem concerns the 'grid-search' for the primary position (cf. NDAC/LO/089). It appears that this search fails in about half of the cases when the system parameters are close to the "worst" case (sep=0.65 arcsec, dm=0, zero ecliptic latitude). This high failing-rate is diminished when the assumed true-IC primary and relative position errors are diminished, as shown in Table 1. Also, the failing-rate diminishes rapidly with increasing dm, as shown by the data in Table 2.

Table 1. Number of failed grid-searches for the primary position for 8.5+8.5 systems with Sep=0".65, dm=0, at ecliptic latitude 6 deg.

pr err	rel err	# runs	#failed	%failed
1".25	0".25	75	40	53
0".75	0".30	25	13	52
0".75	0".25	50	16	32
0".75	0".20	25	5	20
0".75	0".15	25	4	16
0".75	0".10	25	4	16

Table 2. Number of failed grid-searches as function of the magnitude difference for the same standard systems as in Table 1. (Pr and rel err 1".25 and 0".25).

dm	#runs	#failed	%failed
0.0	75	40	53
0.25	40	8	20
0.50	50	4	8
0.75	40	3	8

The failing rate does diminish with increasing ecliptic latitude, but slowly, to (say) three fourths of the zero-latitude rate at 30 degrees. All grid-searches are made with an assumed (erroneous) value for the magnitude-difference between the components. In the present runs, the standard deviation for this dm-error is 0.3 magnitudes, but a single series of runs with 0.1 mag standard deviation did not give fewer grid-search failings.

In conclusion, high grid-search failing-rates will be observed for a small number of "special" systems. A good knowledge of the relative positions of the components reduces the problem, and in most cases, an enlarged search may in the end find a sufficiently good primary position for the LS solution proper to converge.

(A potentially worse problem may be a (say) 3% failing-rate for "normal" systems. This is not easily discovered when experiments number only in the tens, but it may be quite annoying when the (real) number of cases nears 10000. The final performance of the grid-search will depend heavily on the actual precision of the Input Catalogue data, and some flexibility of method may be necessary in this part of the Double Star processing).